

Project-based learning applied to improve the performance of a family wine bottling unit

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6924292>

Abstract

This article aims to show the effect of the application of concepts and principles of some operational excellence models, such as Lean Thinking and Shingo Model, in a family wine bottling unit. The project was carried out by a group of students in a project-based learning mode in the curricular unit "Lean Management and Organization" of the Master's degree in Systems Engineering at the University of Minho. The objective of the project is to implement actions and improve the overall performance of the wine bottling unit. The students started by making an analysis and diagnosis of the initial state of that production unit, identifying problems and opportunities for improvement, and introducing improvements that led to better performance. The main concepts and principles applied were value and waste identification; transport, movement and defect waste reduction; production in flow; and process focus. They managed to better balance the line, improve flow, reduce defects and increase productivity.

Keywords: Project Based Learning; Excellence Models; Lean Thinking.

1 Introduction

Over the years, there has been an increase in competitiveness in the world market, which together with the emergence of an increasingly demanding consumer, forced the evolution of production systems. Within that, the Lean philosophy emerged, which, according to Liker (1997) can be defined as an organizational model that seeks to eliminate waste and increase the agility and efficiency of the value stream. The concept of waste can be defined as any activity that uses resources, but doesn't produce any type of value and can be classified as: overproduction, when more is produced or before the moment is necessary; transport, when there is unnecessary movement of products/materials; inventory, when there is an excess of stored materials or products; waiting, when there is waste time waiting for the next step; overprocessing, when there is more work or higher quality than required by the customer; defects, when there is effort caused by defects, reworks and incorrect information; movement, when there is an unnecessary movement of people; human potential, when talent, skills and knowledge are wasted (Womack and Jones, 2003; Ohno, 1998).

To assist the identification of waste, Value Stream Mapping (VSM) (Rother & Shook, 1999)(Jones & Womack, 2002) can be used as a Lean tool to analyze and model production processes and, consequently, identify activities that add/don't add value (Busert & Fay, 2020). In addition, to monitor and evaluate the evolution of production, a set of performance indicators is used, aimed at eliminating waste, efficient use of resources and better control of the production process (Mourtzis et al., 2017).

The article describes the application of theoretical knowledge in a practical context with the aim of improving a family wine bottling line where production problems and operating difficulties were observed. The main objective is to understand how the application of Lean principles and techniques have an impact on a production line. In this way, it is intended to carry out an analysis of the production line and identify opportunities for improvement, collect data and information for analysis, propose and implement improvements and perform comparisons in the performance before and after the proposed changes.

In a first phase, in order to have a real perception of the production line, the group went to the farm, on a bottling day, and observed its operation. In addition, processing times were also accounted for in order to ensure the possibility of comparing performance indicators with the improvements implemented.

Then, to assess the state of the bottling line, a VSM was created, and some relevant performance indicators were established. In this way, it was possible to identify in which sections of the line improvements could be applied and/or problems that occurred during the analysis of the line could be solved. That said, a set of actions was developed and later implemented on the line, in order to account for new process performance indicators. After all the implementations, the new operation of the line was analyzed, and conclusions were drawn to understand the impact of lean techniques implemented in the bottling line.

The present article was developed by a group of students, within the scope of the curricular unit Management and Lean Organization, taught in the Master's degree in Systems Engineering at the University of Minho. The project was developed during the second semester of the academic year 2021/2022, and a group of three elements implemented the techniques taught in the curricular unit to this practical case. The curriculum of Master's degree in Systems Engineering aims to provide students a strong practical component on all the following curricular units: logistics, simulation, production management, supply chain optimization, systems analysis, similarity based systems, advanced database administration and exploration and two integrated projects. These two integrated projects are carried out over an entire semester and it's important to mention that they combine all the other units. The present project developed in the lean management and organization curricular unit fits in the Master's curriculum since there is a link between the course, the production and the industry so it is important to know the techniques learned in this unit. It also provides the practical component that becomes a valuable point for the students' learning, especially since it is a project-based learning.

At the beginning of the semester, the teacher explained the context of the project to the students, being that no specific theme was given to them, it was only necessary to apply all the knowledge that were being acquired throughout the unit to a practical case chosen by the group. The group decided to apply the project in a company context and the first task was to select it. After the selection, the group defined milestones to achieve a member responsible for having the most contact between the company and the group/teacher. Given the characteristics of the business, wine bottling was not yet being executed at the beginning of the project, so the group decided to visit the farm and study some aspects of wine bottling characteristics according to workers interviews and through a simulation of the line production. When the line was finally working, the group divided tasks among the members, to increase productivity, and was given a deadline to every task in order for the group to fulfill the plan initially defined.

2 Initial State

The Quinta Portal da Veiga is a family wine company located in Guimarães, region in the north of Portugal. The farm produces red, rosy and white "vinho verde"⁴. The winemaking process ends with the bottling of the wine, which takes place from December to March, on previously planned days, because of the long setup times required to prepare the bottling wine. Another restriction is that when the wine is transferred to the refrigeration tank, it has to be emptied by the end of each bottling day.

The current bottling line considered in this study needs five operators assigned to five processes. Before each bottling day, the bottles required for that day are washed in advance and stored in baskets as shown in Figure 1. Left, with fifty bottles each.

⁴ "Vinho verde" is the type of wine produced in the northwest part of Portugal

Figure 1. Storage of washed bottles (left); Process 1 (right).⁴

In process 1 the operator collects empty bottles from the baskets and places them in the filling machine. Once inside the machine, the filling is automatic, and each bottle always takes the same amount of wine, which is mixed with the gas. This process takes about 4.49 seconds per bottle.

The process 2 (Figure 2 on the left) also requires one operator interacting continuously with process 1, since it consists of removing the bottle from the filling machine and passing it on to the worker of the next process. This process takes about 3.99 seconds per bottle.

Figure 2. Process 2 (left) and Process 3 (right).

The operator in Process 3 takes the bottle that comes from process 2, places it in the bottle corking machine and presses a button to initiate an automatic introduction of a cork stopper in the bottle. This process takes in average 3.99 seconds per bottle.

In Process 4 (see left side of Figure 3) the operator collects the bottle that comes from the previous process, places a plastic capsule on the bottle neck and inserts the bottle into the bottle capsulator machine for a short period of time, so that the plastic melts and stays fixed to the bottle. The time of this process is 5.84 seconds per bottle.

Figure 3. Process 4 (left) and Process 5 (right).

Finally, in Process 5 an operator transports six bottles at a time taking them by hand to the storage location. This process has a time per bottle of 3.53 seconds.

2.1 KPIs Analysis

The line configuration presented has a *bottleneck* in process 4, resulting in a cycle time of 5.84 seconds per bottle. Table 1 presents data and KPI results from the observation and analysis of one day. Due to 5 workers hired, the productivity of 123 bottles/man.hour and the labor utilization rate of 60.53% was determined. The processing time, that is, the sum of times of all processes is 20.68 seconds, which results in a line efficiency of 70.81%. In this way the line is only able to fill 3785 bottles in an 8-hour shift, equivalent to 400 minutes of work. On the observed day 84 defective bottles were produced, so a quality factor of 97.8% was determined. The OEE (*Overall Equipment Effectiveness*) was also determined resulting in a value of 74.9% with a speed factor of 83.2% and an availability factor of 92.1%.

Table2. Data on the current state of the bottling line

Data collected	Value	KPI	Value
Number of employees	5	Line Cycle Time	5.84 seconds
Parts produced	3785	Productivity	123 bottles/man.hour
Total Processing Time	20.69 seconds	Line efficiency	70,81%
Total manpower time	17.68 seconds	Labor utilization rate	60,53%
Opening time	400 minutes	OEE	92,1%
Unplanned downtime	31.6 minutes	Availability factor	83,2%
Defective produced parts	84	Speed factor	97,8%
		Quality factor	74,9%

2.2 Waste identification

Once the operation of the line was analyzed, a VSM (Value Stream Mapp) was created, with the objective of being able to describe the whole process and identify the main problems and some existing types of waste. Given the characteristics of the business, the VSM only corresponds to the bottling period.

Customers go to the farm on average once a day and buy 2 boxes of 12 bottles. Suppliers, who are contacted by telephone call by the production manager, go to the farm only once a year and bring all the necessary stock (capsules and cork stoppers), except for the bottle supplier, which moves once a week.

Regarding the processes, 5 types of waste were identified: motion, defect, transport and overproduction. Motion waste was observed in processes 1 and 2, because operators are constantly replacing empty baskets with baskets with bottles. Defective waste occurs in all processes: in process 1 and process 2, it occurs when the filling of the bottles becomes unbalanced and the bottles become a little empty; in case 3, it is verified when the bottle explodes at the moment the cork stopper is put; in process 4, it happens when the bottle explodes, because the operator leaves it in the machine too long; in process 5, occurs when the operator drops a bottle to the ground and leaves. The waste with transport is observed in process 5, when the operator moves through the cellar to the storage area of the bottles. Finally, overproduction is wasted when it is produced first than necessary. However, this waste is considered as necessary due to the characteristics of the business.

Additionally, in addition to these wastes, one of the main problems of the line is the accumulation of WIP between process 3 and 4, because in process 4, there are actually two operations: putting the capsule and putting the bottle in the machine. Thus, the operator, before putting the bottle into the machine, always has to check that the bottle already has capsule and, while putting capsules, has to check that no bottle has forgotten in the machine, which means that it is a more time-consuming process, which marks the cadence of the line.

Figure 4. Value Stream Mapping (VSM).

3 Proposals for improvements

In view of the identified waste, we sought to propose solutions that would allow its elimination or its reduction. The first proposed solution is the acquisition of *fastrack wine supports*, as they take up little space and are quite stable. Given that the space for basket storage is of about 15 square meters and the proposed solution, considering 3 levels, needs about 7 square meters and would be possible to be implement. However, an investment of €660 would be required.

Figure 5. Example of a *fastrack wine holder* (Fast Brewing & Wine Making, 2018)

In fact, this solution would reduce waste with motion in processes 1 and 2, as operators would not need to be constantly picking up a heavy basket to replace the empty baskets. In addition, it would reduce the defective waste that occurs in process 3, because with the new arrangement of the bottles, the bottlenecks would be away from each other, and the glass would always be intact. It should be noted that the arrangement of the deflating bottles of the baskets causes the necks to exert pressure on each other, which gives rise to fractures in the glass that then give in to the pressure of the cork stopper.

The second suggested solution consists of the use of two cases between processes 4 and 5, which make it possible to carry 12 bottles simultaneously. Thus, it was intended for the worker in workstation 4 to place the bottles in one of the baskets instead of placing them on the table, whereas during this period the worker in workstation 5 would be placing the bottles in the storage area. Consequently, when he returned to his post, he would have a new complete box to make a new transport. However, after implementing this solution, it

was found that the worker in post 5 had enough waiting periods and to eliminate this waste, it was considered that this worker should help the worker in post 4 to put capsules.

Having said that, in process 5, the waste with transport is reduced, since the worker can carry 12 bottles in a single movement, and the defective waste is eliminated, since the boxes prevent some bottle from falling to the ground. In addition, there is a reduction of WIP between process 3 and 4 and a decrease in the waste verified in process 4, since with the help of the worker of process 5, the worker of this process can be more focused on the bottles he puts in the machine.

In addition to the improvements implemented in the line, the 5S methodology (Hirano, 1995) was also implemented, in order to keep the winery and materials organized and reduce the cleaning time of the space whenever an unplanned stop occurs, in view of the occurrence of defects in production.

In the separation (Seiri), the necessary objects were separated from the unneeded ones. For this, the red tag strategy was used with the identification of the object and the reason for it to be discarded. In the red tag area defined, the objects must be kept for one month and then the owner of the farm must make a final decision in relation to their usefulness.

Figure 6. Implemented red tag area (left) and Organization of materials (right)

Then the space was organized (Seitou) so as to be simpler and more intuitive to find the materials, having placed some identifying papers.

Regarding cleaning (Seiso), despite the care of the workers, they usually used baskets to store the garbage and therefore the only aspect implemented was the addition of a dustbin.

For the Seiketsu (Standardize) process, visual management was used with instructions in the various spaces and in relation to the last Shitsuke (Keep), the line is responsible for naming a person who on each day of bottling, before starting the shift, verify that the 5S rules are being complied with and that the space is properly organized.

4 Futures State

The new line configuration allowed reducing the cycle time to 4.49 seconds, maintaining the same number of employees, which improves the various KPIs analyzed previously. Considering the same time of operation of the line (400 minutes), the most significant improvements are the increase in productivity to 160 bottles/man, quantity of parts produced for 4981 bottles, reduction of defective parts and the various times of operation of the line. The positive impacts are reflected in the availability factor, speed and quality, contributing to an increase in the OEE to 77.5%.

Table 2. Data on the future state of the bottling line

KPI	Value	Value
Cycle time	5.84 seconds	4.49 seconds
Number of employees	5	5
Productivity	123 bottles/hour.	160 bottles/hour.
Processing time	20.69 seconds	17.33 seconds

Total manpower time	17.68 seconds	14.33 seconds
Line efficiency	70,81%	77,18%
Labor utilization rate	60,53%	63,82%
Opening time	400 minutes	400 minutes
Unplanned downtime	31.6 minutes	27 minutes
Parts produced per day	3785	4981
Defective produced parts per day	84	67
Availability factor	92,1%	93,2%
Speed factor	83,2%	84,3%
Quality factor	97,8%	98,65%
Overall Equipment Effectiveness	74,9%	77,5%

5 Conclusion

This article, developed in real context by a group of systems engineering students in a family wine company, identified opportunities for improvement in the company under study.

The project helped students to understand the impact of lean principles and techniques application in the production process with a practical use case. Additionally, the experience contributed to understand that a successful teamwork needs a very solid communication and a distribution of tasks according team's members skills.

This work also contributed to the students learning process, with the increase of their motivation as part of a natural process with an outside collaboration and in the development of important skills for their future professional path, like critical thinking and teamwork spirit.

In this paper, the following improvements in line performance should be highlighted: decreased cycle time, significantly increase in line productivity and efficiency, decrease in defective parts per day and a very satisfactory increase in OEE in the face of implementing improvements.

In addition to the improvements verified with the monitoring of performance indicators, the lean improvements implemented, allowed workers to operate more safely in their workplace and are less subject to any accidents that may occur when a bottle leaves. The implementation of the 5S also brought significant advantages with regard to the organization of the winery, with the main benefit of speeding up unplanned stops when problems occur on the line.

Since the main objective of this project was to apply the knowledge acquired in lean classes in a practical context, the work developed falls within that scope and for that the results were successfully obtained.

The project evaluation was divided in two phases. Firstly, in the middle of the semester, the students introduced the company to the teacher, showed videos about the processes and presented some preliminary results. At the end of the semester, the final results were discussed with other systems engineering students. On both occasions, the teacher has given feedback to improve the quality of the project and provided an evaluation about the topics discussed and the level of the group communication.

Finally, the main challenge faced with the realization of the project was to overcome the resistance of employees in the face of the improvements that the group intended to implement. However, the project allowed the group to understand the concepts taught through their application in a real context.

Acknowledgments

This work was partially supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020.

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